

Doreen has recently graduated from a master in early modern history and is desperately looking for a job. One day, she receives an email from her thesis supervisor. He is friends with a senior historian from the United States who is looking for someone to do archival research for his new book on 17th century diplomatic relations between Persia and the Dutch Republic. The senior historian is not able to read old Dutch handwriting, and therefore needs (paid) help. Doreen is very happy to be able to contribute to a project in her field. After a Zoommeeting with the American professor she starts right away. The professor instructs her what parts of the archives she should transcribe and translate. Doreen gives regular updates on her findings in the Dutch archives. After six months she is finished and delivers a final assessment of her results. When the book is ready after a few years, Doreen is very curious. Soon, she notices that her name is not mentioned, while the American historian did use many transcriptions she made of relevant material in the Dutch archives.

- 1) Is the senior American historian obligated to mention the name of Doreen, although she did not interpret the sources? Could you define this as plagiarism?
- 2) Is the book of the American historian valid, if he was not able to read the original sources himself?